

Systematic method development and validation with an Analytical Quality by Design and UPLC

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Abstract

This work describes a chromatographic technique for quantifying Azilsartan and Cilnidipine in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations using Quality by Design (QbD). The Analytical Targeting Profile (ATP) distribution and Critical Analytical Attributes (CAA) are incorporated with Analytical Quality by Design. The application of Central Composite Designs was used to optimize the process. Selected CMPs, such as Rt of peak2, Plate count of peak 2 (R2), and tailing factor of peak 2 (R3) were evaluated. The individual and interaction effects of CMP on CAA were assessed using statistical data and response surface plots. The significance ($P < 0.05$) of the procedure parameters was shown by analysis of variance (ANOVA). Mobile phase- Buffer (0.1% TEA pH 2.5 adjusted with OPA) and Methanol (80:20), and Zorbax RRHD eclipse plus C₁₈ (50 x 2.1mm, 1.8 μ m) the flow rate is 0.4 ml/minute with photodiode array detector at 294 nm. According to ICH requirements, method validation and subsequent stress degradation experiments were carried out. All variables are within their bounds. The suggested method is effectively illustrated using a QbD to perform extremely sensitive, stable, and suited for regular analysis and clinical applications.

Keywords: Elbasvir, Grazoprevir, QbD, UPLC, Validation

INTRODUCTION

Elbasvir is a non-structural protein 5A (NS5A) inhibitor that is used to prevent the Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) from replicating its genetic material and assembling its virion. (Sumalatha *et al.*, 2017) After delivery, elbasvir has a 32% absolute bioavailability and reaches its peak plasma concentration 3-6 hours later. ELB's IUPAC name is methyl N-[(2S)-1-[(2S)-2-[5-[(6S)-3-[2-[(2S)-1-[(2S)-1-[(2S)-1-[(2S)-1-[(2S)-1-3-methylbutanol-2-(methoxycarbonyl amino)-3-methylbutanoyl] pyrrolidine-2-yl]-1H-imidazol-5-yl]-6-phenyl-6H-indolo[1,2-c][1,3]benzoxazin-10-yl]-1H-imidazol-2-yl]pyrrolidin-1-yl]-3-methyl-1-oxobutan-2-yl]carbamate (4th). $C_{49}H_{55}N_9O_7$ is the chemical formula for ELB. ELB has a molecular weight of 882 g/mol. The structure is depicted in fig 1.

Fig 1. Structure of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir

Grazoprevir is an NS3/4a protease inhibitor of the second generation that is used to stop the spread of HCV. The Grazoprevir IUPAC name is (1aR,5S,8S,10R,22aR)-N-[(1R,2S)-1-[(Cyclopropylsulfonamido)carbonyl]-2-ethenylcyclopropyl]-14-methoxy-5-(2-methylpropan-2-yl)-3,6-dioxo-1,1a,3,4,5,6,9,10,18,19,20,21,22,22a-tetradecahydro-8H-7,10-methanocyclopropa

Extensive literature survey revealed that few analytical methods were reported in the literature to determine ELB and GRZ by UV Spectrophotometric method by dual-wavelength (DW), classic least-squares (CLS), and principal component regression (PCR) method (Khalid A.M. Attia *et al.*, 2018) RP-HPLC (Aymen Labidi *et al.*, 2021, Girija Dandu *et al.*, 2020, Lakshmi Surekha *et al.*, 2019, Pavan Kumar *et al.*, 2018, and Akram *et al.*, 2017), in bulk and solid dosage form. To date, no reports on QbD-based stability indicate the Reverse Phase Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatographic (RP-UPLC) method.

Hence, the present study was planned to develop and validate stability indicating simultaneous estimation of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms using the Experimental Design approach.

MATERIALS and METHODS

ELB with powder purity containing 99.0% w/w was obtained from Jubilant Biosys Ltd. Bengaluru, India and GRZ was obtained from Glenmark with powder purity containing 100.1% w/w Pharmaceutical Ltd., Hyderabad, India. The formulation of these drugs was commercially available under the trade name ZEPATIER (Merck & Co., Inc.) tablet. Agilent UPLC system from Agilent1290 Infinity II LC System (Agilent Infinity lab suppliers). The system also includes a Photodiode Array (PDA) Detector. Design Expert® from the State-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, MN (Version 12.0) was used for experimental design and interpretation.

ELB and GRZ solutions were prepared in the concentrations of 50g/ml and 100g/ml, respectively. The amount of organic solvent in the mobile phase (X1), the pH of the mobile phase (X2), and the flow rate (X3) are the three independent variables that were taken into account when developing the procedure. The responses employed in the experimental design are displayed in Table 4.1 and include the grazoprevir retention duration (Y1), predicted plate count of peak 2 (Y2), and tailing factor of peak 2 (Y3). As stated in Table 4.2, low (-1) and high (+1) levels were chosen for all independent variables.

The objectives of the work were to validate the RP-UPLC method optimized by QbD for simultaneous estimation of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir according to ICH Q2 R (1) guidelines for system suitability, specificity, accuracy, precision, linearity, robustness, and LOD and LOQ.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Chromatographic Conditions for Developed Method

Column : Zorbax RRHD eclipse plus C₁₈ (50 x 2.1mm, 1.8 μ m)
 Wavelength : 294 nm
 Injection Volume : 5 μ L
 Column Temperature : Ambient
 Flow rate : 0.4mL/min
 Mobile Phase : Buffer (0.1% TEA pH 2.5 adjusted with OPA) and Methanol (80:20)
 The retention time of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir were found at 1.086 and 2.346 min respectively.

A 3-factor, 3-level Box-Behnken design was utilized to generate polynomial models for the optimization process because it requires few runs with three or four variables.

Table 1. Results of selected responses in BBD for 17 runs

Experimental Run	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3
	A: Organic Phase Ratio	B: pH of Buffer	C: Flow Rate	Rt of Peak2	Plate Count of Peak2	Tailing Factor of Peak2
1	20	3.5	0.4	2.181	9809	0.84
2	30	2.5	0.5	1.724	9883	0.82
3	20	3	0.5	2.042	9883	0.92
4	20	3	0.5	2.043	9861	0.87
5	10	3	0.4	2.416	9752	0.88
6	20	3	0.5	2.045	9838	0.86
7	20	3.5	0.6	1.694	9842	0.85
8	30	3.5	0.5	1.814	9842	0.86
9	10	3	0.6	2.772	9834	0.89
10	30	3	0.6	1.789	9839	0.85
11	20	3	0.5	2.046	9863	0.88
12	20	2.5	0.6	2.312	9842	0.85
13	20	3	0.5	2.427	9852	0.88
14	10	2.5	0.5	2.37	9797	0.89
15	20	2.5	0.4	2.33	9812	0.79
16	30	3	0.4	1.543	9849	0.82
17	10	3.5	0.5	2.65	9799	0.88

Effect of method variables (X₁, X₂, X₃) on Responses:

The quadratic model's generated polynomial equations for each answer are displayed below.

$$Y_1=2.93X_1+0.4371X_2+4.58X_3+4.67X_1X_2+1.12X_1X_3+2.18X_2X_3+7.42X_1^2+1.47X_2^2+3.37X_3^2.$$

$$Y_2=6670.13X_1+220.50X_2+2278.12X_3+462.25X_1X_2+2116.00X_1X_3+2.25X_2X_3+1433.27X_1^2+482.06X_2^2+2122.12X_3^2$$

$$Y_3=0.0045X_1+0.0008X_2+0.0015X_3+0.0006X_1X_2+0.0001X_1X_3+0.0006X_2X_3+0.0001X_1^2+0.0023X_2^2+0.0023X_3^2.$$

These formulas showed the impact of the proportion of variables and responses squared, individually, and collectively. A negative number denotes an inverse association between the component and the response, whilst a positive value suggests an effect that is favorable to the responses.

ANOVA

The adjusted R-squared value and the anticipated R-squared values of the grazoprevir retention duration (Y_1), plate of peak 2 (Y_2), and tailing factor (Y_3) were in reasonable agreement. The difference is less than 0.2. The signal-to-noise ratio is measured with adequate precision. It is preferable to have a ratio larger than 4. For Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 , the appropriate precision values were 9.6485, 11.7779, and 6.9920, respectively.

The responses for the grazoprevir Rt (Y_1), plate of peak2 (Y_2), and tailing factor (Y_3) had model F-values of 11.84, 9.35, and 4.70, respectively, indicating that the model is significant. The model terms may be significant if the values of the significant responses revealed a p-value of less than 0.05. There was a strong correlation between the experimental data and the fitted models, as evidenced by the low standard deviation and high adjusted R-square value.

Table 2. ANOVA

Source	F-value	P-value	Adequate precision	Predicted R ² -value	Adjusted R ² -value	Results
R1						
Model	13493.14	< 0.0001	9.6485	0.4979	0.6702	significant
Lack of Fit	5.27	0.0711				not significant
R2						
Model	5975.62	< 0.0001	11.7779	0.6636	0.8245	significant
Lack of Fit	1.97	0.2605				not significant
R3						
Model	1293.64	< 0.0001	6.9920	0.6194	0.6757	significant
Lack of Fit	3.65	0.1216				not significant

Perturbation, 2D-Contour and 3D-Response surface plots:

Perturbation plots were evaluated to study the effect of factors on the responses which revealed that the factor, organic solvent ratio (X_1) contributed more in altering the Y_2 and Y_3 when compared to other factors (X_2 and X_3) for both drugs ELB and GRZ shown in Fig 2.

Contour and response surface plots were analyzed to visualize the effect of the factors and their interactions on the responses (David et al., 2012). Fig 3, 4 and 5. a 2D contour and b 3D response surface plots that portray the effect of mobile phase and pH of buffer on retention time of grazoprevir (Y_1) and peak tailing of grazoprevir (Y_3). In response surface plots, at low levels of X_1 and X_2 , the retention time of Y_1 and Y_2 decreased. On the other hand, keeping the organic solvent at a low level, with increasing pH of buffer there was an increase in the plate count of peak 2. Hence the Rt of grazoprevir decreases with an increase in the mobile phase ratio. At a higher level of pH buffer, a low level of organic ratio increases the tailing of peak 2.

Fig 2: Perturbation plot showing the effect of mobile phase (X_1), pH of the mobile phase (X_2), and flow rate (X_3) on Responses. a) Y_1 , b) Y_2 , c) Y_3

Figure 3: a) 2D contour and b) 3D response surface plots for Y_1

Fig 4: a) 2D contour and b) 3D response surface plots for Y_2

Fig 5: a) 2D contour and b) 3D response surface plots for Y_3

Validation of the model

The percentage anticipated error was found to be below 15%, namely in the range of -0.303 to 1.7%, suggesting that the observed answers were quite similar to the predicted responses. The response surface methodology's strong predicting capabilities for the chosen design were validated.

Through examination of residual plots and linear correlation plots between the actual (observed) and projected responses, as displayed in Figure 6, the suitability of the model was assessed. The goodness of fit was shown by the correlation's high R-square values for Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 (0.7320, 0.9232, and 0.8581, respectively). Thus, the high predictive capacity of the RSM was demonstrated by the low magnitudes of error and the R^2 values.

Fig 6: Residual plots for the various variables

Optimization of multiple responses:

The method was optimized by numerical optimization of the dependent (response) variables Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3 and the desirable range of the independent variables (factors). The values between $10 \leq X_1 \leq 30$, $2.5 \leq X_2 \leq 3.5$, and $0.4 \leq X_3 \leq 0.60$, whereas the desirable ranges of responses were Y_1 (1.650), Y_2 (9826.164) and Y_3 (0.829) which indicated desirable regression ranges with an overall desirability of 0.955

Based on desirability optimized chromatographic conditions were selected shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Optimized chromatographic conditions by QbD

S. No	Name	Condition
1	Mobile phase	Methanol+ 0.1% TEA pH-2.5/OPA (80:20)
2	Column	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 (100mm x 2.1, 1.7 μ m)
3	Flow rate	0.3 ml/min

4	Wavelength	294 nm
5	Injection volume	5µl
6	Temperature	25°C
7	Detector	PDA

Fig 7: Optimized Chromatogram

Name	Retention Time	Area	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
Elbasvir	0.561	1255780	10236	0.71	
Grazoprevir	1.655	3041584	9660	0.92	13.45

Method Validation

As per ICH guidelines, the proposed method was validated by different parameters like System Suitability, Specificity, Linearity, Limit of Detection, Limit of Quantification, Precision, Accuracy, and Robustness.

(i) System Suitability

Validation experiments using 50g/mL Elbasvir and 100g/mL Grazoprevir were used to assess the system applicability of the optimized method. The results were found to be within the limits.

(ii) Specificity

The specificity of the method was evaluated to assess the interference of impurities which will be useful for evaluation of its interferences of excipients in the dosage form. The chromatogram of the blank and (Fig 8) and sample solution (Fig 9) obtained by this method indicated the absence of interfering peaks. So, this method was said to be specific.

Fig 8: Chromatogram of Blank

Fig 9: Sample chromatogram

(iii) Accuracy:

Table 4 displays the percentage recovery and mean recovery percentages for each accuracy level, which were determined using triplicate injections. The percentage mean recovery was found to be 99.6 and 100.2% for Elbasvir and Grazoprevir respectively which are within the limits i.e. 98-102%, thus the method was found to be accurate.

Table 4: Results for Accuracy

Recovery Sample Name	Elbasvir		Grazoprevir	
	% Recovery	Mean	% Recovery	Mean
50% -1	100.0	99.46	100.4	99.7
50% -2	98.4		99.2	
50% -3	100.0		99.6	
100% -1	99.6	99.86	101.4	100.5
100% -2	101.6		99.6	
100% -3	98.4		100.6	
150% -1	100.3	99.3	100.1	100.4
150% -2	99.2		100.4	
150% -3	98.4		100.9	
Mean± SD	99.6±0.306		100.2±0.462	
%RSD	0.31		0.46	

Precision

Six replicate injections of standard preparation of elbasvir (50µg/ml) and grazoprevir (100µg/ml) were injected into a UPLC system and calculated %RSD as shown in Table 5 and was found to be within the limits (<2), which indicated that the developed method was precise.

Table 5: System, Method and Intermediate Precision

Sample	Elbasvir			Grazoprevir		
	Area SP	Area MP	Area IP	Area SP	Area MP	Area IP
1	1265065	1249071	1256123	3037401	3025648	3027654
2	1268651	1265840	1248154	3039513	3071256	3003216
3	1257250	1275354	1271854	3042170	3035642	3046241
4	1260798	1255361	1280215	3030128	3048143	3067548
5	1263512	1249214	1266974	3026354	3072874	3058452
6	1259446	1260521	1271020	3047434	3054123	3050543
Mean ± SD	1262454 ± 4128.23	1259227± 10235.59	1265726 ± 11645.26	3037167± 7777.77	3051281 ± 18893.44	3042276 ± 23340.47
%RSD	4128.23	0.813	0.92	0.256	0.619	0.767

Linearity

The best-fit line was determined by preparing proportional linear concentrations of both the drugs in the range of 12.5 µg/ml to 75 µg/ml for elbasvir and 25 µg/ml to 150 µg/ml for grazoprevir and calibration curves were plotted (Figure 10&11) with its respective peak area. The method confirmed the linearity within the selected range of concentrations of two drugs.

Figure 10&11: Calibration curves for Elbasvir and Grazoprevir

Sensitivity:

According to ICH standards Q2 (R1), the signal-to-noise ratio standard deviation technique was used to determine the LOD and LOQ. The method's sufficient sensitivity was indicated by the low values of LOD for ELB and GRZ were found to be 0.15 and 0.3µg/ml and LOQ was 0.5 and 1 µg/ml respectively.

Robustness

There was no discernible variation in the peak area in Table 6 across all chromatographic conditions, including acetonitrile volume, flow rate, and wavelength changes. The % RSD was determined to be substantially within the limits (<2%), indicating the technique was robust.

Table 6: Results for Robustness

Parameter	Elbasvir			Grazoprevir		
	Area	% Assay	%RSD*	Area	%Assay	% RSD*
Flow Rate						
Flow-rate 0.55ml/min	1447462	101.6	0.47	3131487	99.1	1.04
	1436951	100.9		3194123	101.1	
	1450654	101.8		3178524	100.6	
0.45 ml/min	1025204	98.8	1.21	2862369	100.7	0.55
	1043591	100.6		2831478	99.6	
	1048672	101.1		2847568	100.2	
Organic Phase Ratio						
Organic Plus 33	1583567	99.8	0.63	3354324	99.7	0.48
	1579851	99.5		3325841	98.8	
	1565160	98.6		3332224	99.0	
Organic Minus	1159849	101.3	0.99	2753640	99.5	0.57
	1139247	99.5		2783810	100.6	

27	1142318	99.7		2761564	99.8	
Wavelength						
Wavelength Plus 299	1583567	99.8	0.63	3348789	99.5	0.41
	1579851	99.5		3333254	99.0	
	1565160	98.6		3321698	98.7	
Wavelength Minus 289	1129756	98.6	0.63	2726583	98.5	0.96
	1139244	99.5		2748320	99.3	
	1125302	98.3		2779645	100.4	

Assay:

The optimized method was tested for its application to estimate the two drugs in tablet (Zepetair) dosage form by conducting the assay. The results of the assay in terms of percentage drug content were calculated by comparing the peak area of both drugs for their standards as shown in Table 4.16. The average % drug content in the assay obtained for both drugs were 99.9 and 100.1% respectively which is in good agreement with the % label claim by the developed method of UPLC which confirmed the suitability of the method for estimation of drugs simultaneously in its dosage forms.

Fig 12: Assay chromatogram

Forced degradation studies

The % degradation of two drugs along with their purity angle and purity threshold were found to be within the limits, the purity angle was found to be less than that of the purity threshold which confirmed that the developed method was stability indicating. The highest degradation (13.4%) was observed in peroxide condition and the lowest (1.4%) was in hydrolysis.

Table 7: Forced Degradation

Sample exposure condition	% Degradation		Purity angle		Purity threshold	
	ELB	GRZ	ELB	GRZ	ELB	GRZ
Control	0	0	2.869	1.427	8.044	2.132
Acidic	10.8	13.1	2.855	1.444	8.025	2.124
Alkali	11.5	14.4	2.817	1.416	8.054	2.165
Peroxide	13.4	13.5	2.828	1.482	8.073	2.154
Reduction	10.2	12.6	2.854	1.469	8.054	2.163
Thermal	1.7	10.6	2.803	1.485	8.077	2.119
Photodegradation	3.7	3.4	2.865	1.497	8.041	2.105
Hydrolysis	1.4	1.1	2.827	1.458	8.079	2.172

Solution Stability

Over the examination of the stability of the solutions, both samples and standard solutions were allowed to be monitored for 24 hours at 105° C. Following the test, it was discovered that the sample and standard solutions were stable for up to the tested period *i.e.*, 24 hours.

Table 8: Solution Stability for Elbasvir & Grazoprevir

Time (Hrs)	Area				% Deviation			
	Standard		Sample		Standard		Sample	
	ELB	GRZ	ELB	GRZ	ELB	GRZ	ELB	GRZ
Initial	1218615	2908248	1208521	2920641	3.5	4.2	4.3	3.8
6 hrs	1209443	2859764	1200254	2872153	4.2	5.8	5	5.4
12 hrs	1190543	2814853	1173703	2795708	5.7	7.3	7.1	7.9
18 hrs	1143397	2751054	1115407	2672211	9.5	9.4	11.7	12
24 hrs	1134963	2715347	1094034	2598338	10.1	10.5	13.4	14.4

CONCLUSION

In the current study, a robust AQbD-based UPLC has been developed and validated. It can be concluded that combining BBD with RSM is a versatile approach for reducing the number of experimental runs and obtaining robust analytics. Hence, the present approach can be successfully employed for routine analysis of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir in Quality control laboratories.

REFERENCES

1. American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases; Infectious Diseases Society of America. HCV guidance. <http://hcvguidelines.org>.
2. Bagaglio S, Uberti-Foppa C, Morsica G: Resistance Mechanisms in Hepatitis C Virus: implications for Direct-Acting Antiviral Use. *Drugs*. 2017 May.
3. National Center for Biotechnology Information (2023). PubChem Compound Summary for CID 71661251, Elbasvir. Retrieved October 4, 2023
4. Nallagundla S, Reddy NH, Vemula V, Kumar B. Analytical method development and validation of elbasvir and grazoprevir in bulk and tablet formulations by Rp-HPLC. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science Invention*. 2017;6(8):01-5.
5. Labidi, A., Jebali, S., Safta, M. *et al.* RP-HPLC Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Determination of Grazoprevir and Elbasvir. *Chemistry Africa* 4, 607–619 (2021).
6. Dr. T. Shyam, K.N. Rajinikanth, Dr. V. Kiran Kumar, Dr. VVSS. Appala Raju, Dr. Macharla Venkata Ramana and Dr. N. Appala Raju. LC-MS/MS Method development and validation for simultaneous quantification of Elbasvis and Grazoprevir in Human plasma. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018; 5(12); 272-281.
7. Surekha ML, Muralikrishna M, Padma R. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of elbasvir and grazoprevir in bulk and tablet dosage forms. *World Journal of Pharm.Scin*. 2019; 8(1):646-657

8. Girija D, Reddy BV. Development and validation of new stability indicating rp-hplc method for simultaneous estimation of elbasvir and grazoprevir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Indian Drugs*. 1;57(9), 2020 Sep
9. Bhimana sasihdar, & Prajapati, S. K. (2016). Analytical method development and validation of elbasvir and grazoprevir in bulk and tablet formulations by RP- HPLC. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Life Sciences*, 4(1), 1-6, 2016.
10. Kumar, V. P., Kumar, A. V., Sivagami, B., Kumar, R. C., & Babu, M. N. Stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of Grazoprevir and Elbasvir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *International Journal of Research In Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis*, 1(1), 1-7. 2018
11. Akram N, Umamahesh M, Ramachari T. A new validated RP-HPLC method for the determination of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir in its bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. *International Journal of Chemical & Pharmaceutical Analysis*. 2017 Apr 1;
12. Khalid A M Attia, Nasr M El-Abasawi, Ahmed El-Olemy, Ahmed H Abdelazim, Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Elbasvir and Grazoprevir in a Pharmaceutical Preparation, *Journal of AOAC INTERNATIONAL*, Volume 101, Issue 2, 394–400 March 2018.
13. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q11: Development and Manufacture of Drug Substances (Chemical Entities and Biotechnological/Biological Entities) (May 2011).
14. Borman, P.; Nethercote, P.; Chatfield, M.; Thompson, D.; Truman K. The Application of Quality by Design to Analytical Methods. *Pharm. Tech.* 2007, 31(12) 142-152.
15. Schweitzer, M.; Pohl, M.; Hanna-Brown, M.; Nethercote, P.; Borman, P.; Hansen, G.; Smith, K.; Larew J. Implications and Opportunities of Applying QbD Principles to Analytical Measurements. *Pharm. Tech.* 2010, 34 (2) 52-59.
16. Vogt, F.G.; Kord A.S. Development of Quality-By-Design Analytical Methods. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 2011, 100(3), 797-812.
17. Bhatt, D.A.; Rane, S.I. QbD Approach to Analytical RP-HPLC Method Development and its Validation. *Int. J. Pharm. and Pharm. Sci.* 2011, 3(1) 179-187.
18. Krull, I.; Swartz, M.; Turpin, J.; Lukulay, P.H.; Verseput, R. A Quality-by-Design Methodology for Rapid LC Method Development, Part I. *LCGC N. Am.* 2008, 26, 1190-1197.